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Introduction of Wet Rice Cultivation In Assam And The Role of The Ahoms: A Vexed Historiography

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Abstract

The scenario in terms of agricultural patterns of Brahmaputra valley during the advent of Ahoms in medieval Assam is vaguely debated. Marxist historian, Amalendu Guha opines that it were the Ahoms that made a giant leap in the transition of the rice culture in upper Assam by introducing and exploring wet-rice cultivation in the land. Guha opines that wet rice culture was traditional with the Ahoms and it was also much more productive than the prevalent dominant rice cultures in the valley. They had also a developed technique of growing transplanted rice on wet, permanent fields, whereas their tribal neighbours practised wasteful shifting cultivation. However, controversy as an inevitable part in history, Guha's interpretations also has been challenged and disputed by many over times. In this paper, a discussion will be made here from a critical standpoint to analyse these interpretations regarding the contribution of the Ahoms towards expansion of the wet-rice cultivation in Medieval Assam.

Key words: *Wet rice cultivation, Ahoms, Medieval Assam, Historiography etc.*

spite of the low population and an apparent shortage of labour force the Ahoms were able to secure their manpower requirements for the purpose of land reclamation and effective hydraulic control quite effectively by devising a very effective system of labour mobilisation and utilisation called the *paik* system. The state machinery was greatly used towards creating the conditions needed for rice cultivation such as land reclamation, flood prevention and water control. Ahom agrarian technology not only ensured a steady supply of food but also the production of sufficient surplus that allowed the Ahom state to executive massive public works, such as roads, embankments, bridges, temples, tanks, palaces and forts. Kakoty thus believes the agrarian technology as the factor that laid the foundation for the building of a strong Ahom state.

Conclusion:

Thus Amalendu Guha has shown how the extension of plough at the cost of hoe cultivation and of wet at the expense of dry rice –lands alongside a general agricultural expansion led to a rapid increase in the surplus produced. According to him a consequent rise in population provided the Ahoms with a material base for their further economic and political expansion. He argued that wet rice culture was traditional with the Ahoms. In his whole study, he is seen taking an interdisciplinary approach incorporating anthropology, sociology and statistics etc while elaborating his observation. However, Guha's analysis of the prevalence of rice culture in Assam before the advent of Ahoms in many times seems puzzling as he himself is seen using the terms like "probably", "it appears that", "nothing is definitely known" etc many times in his discussion. Lahiri strongly asserts that Guha has failed to analyse the continuity between the pre-Ahom and Ahom period. Dhruvajyoti Bora again believes that *Sali* cultivation already existed in lower part of Brahmaputra valley whereas Sanjib Kakoty believes the agrarian technology as the factor that laid the foundation for the building of a strong Ahom state. Furthermore, in the discussion of the state formation process of Ahom state, Guha is seen borrowing heavily from the Engel's notion of state formation hypothesis. But it should also be kept in mind that Engel's theory regarding state formation also has various limitations. However, Guha's interpretations regarding Ahom state formation and transition of wet rice culture by them are no doubt very fresh and innovative. As recent historians have become more aware of the similarity and links between the North East and the East Asian formations, the original contributions of Guha have become more relevant.

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